

Two-year outdoor assessment of perovskite mini-modules: study of diurnal changes and stability outdoors

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Abstract — Several perovskite mini-modules have been installed and tested outdoors for a duration of up to two years. Diurnal performance recovery overnight and diurnal performance degradation of several perovskite samples were calculated for each day in the field demonstrating diurnal values for degradation and recovery up to 30%. Outdoor testing for several months in the field demonstrated the impact of temperature on the major electrical parameters of the devices. Interplay of metastability and temperature effects was detected in the output power temperature coefficient results while agreement was found between indoor and outdoor tests for voltage temperature coefficient results. Finally, perovskite power output time series forecast was implemented for the samples tested for over one year in the field by utilizing different statistical and machine learning methods and gave evidence of good agreement between the actual and predicted power.

I. INTRODUCTION

Perovskite solar cells have been attracting increasing attention in recent years due to their rapid progress with record efficiency of 26.1% for single junction and 33.9% for tandem devices respectively. Even if now perovskites are passing standardized protocols (IEC 61215) and those tests cannot resemble the outdoor operational conditions with day-night cycles and continuous change in temperature and irradiance levels. Till now, a small number of studies have demonstrated long-term outdoor performance monitoring of perovskite-based devices. However, none of outdoor studies so far have taken into consideration the quantitative long-term diurnal changes in degradation and recovery of perovskite samples. Several papers in the past reported that during recovery in the dark, the loss in perovskite device performance under previous light exposure can be fully or partially reversed [1]. Previous reports on the study of temperature effects on perovskite devices have shown that perovskite PV have a smaller (i.e. better) maximum power temperature coefficient at elevated temperatures [2]. To date, there has been little work on determining the temperature coefficients for perovskite photovoltaics indoors and outdoors and more work is needed in this direction. Apart from the investigation of diurnal changes in perovskites and the study of their temperature effects, output power forecasting was implemented on the

outdoor data from perovskite mini modules tested at FOSS testing site. A variety of techniques has evolved the past years to predict the performance of solar power output to characterize the performance at a given location. Some of the most prominent techniques involve the use of mathematical models, statistics, local sensing, satellite imaging and intelligent modules (machine learning and neural networks) [3]. However, due to the limited lifetime of perovskite samples outdoors, very few papers so far report the performance time series prediction using statistical or machine learning models.

In this work, the outdoor stability of several perovskite-based devices (single junction and four-terminal perovskite/Silicon tandems) is reported for a duration of up to two years of testing. Diurnal performance degradation and recovery were calculated for the different structures and demonstrated the dominant values of the degradation and recovery over the testing period. The impact of temperature on the major electrical parameters (open-circuit voltage, maximum output power) was studied and the temperature coefficients extracted outdoors were then compared with indoor laboratory testing. Finally, perovskite performance time series forecast was implemented for the samples tested for over a year in our testing site using different forecasting methods (statistical and machine learning).

II. EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

In total five (5) perovskite mini-modules (single perovskite and four-terminal perovskite/Silicon tandems) have been mounted outdoors in a fixed plane array for different time periods and current-voltage measurements have been collected at regular intervals over several months of outdoor testing. Particularly, two devices with a single perovskite junction (labelled as ETL1-A and ETL2-A) and three four-terminal (4T) perovskite/Silicon tandem devices (labelled as ETL3-A, ETL3-B and ETL3-C) have been studied in the field. One of the single-junction perovskite mini-module (ETL1-A) was tested outdoors for a duration up to two years (July 2021 -July 2023) while the rest of the modules were tested for 1 year. The five samples continue to be tested in the field providing

further information regarding the long-term performance evolution of perovskite-based devices. All the perovskite devices under test have the same perovskite absorber layer ($\text{FA}_{0.8}\text{CS}_{0.2}\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.94}\text{Br}_{0.06})_3$) while they have some differences on their ETL layer. The Silicon bottom cell in the one tandem configuration (labelled as ETL3-Si) was also monitored. Open-circuit loading was applied between the IV scans at almost all instances. Forward and reverse voltage sweeps have been applied during each IV curve trace. Alongside the IV traces from the devices, environmental sensors have been used to collect solar irradiance in the plane of array, ambient and device temperature, wind velocity and humidity/precipitation levels.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Performance Degradation

All the electrical parameters of the modules were collected and analyzed during the whole testing period of the modules. The power conversion efficiency (PCE) of all the modules is depicted in Fig.1. Mean daily values of the reverse sweeps have been taken into consideration for this figure. A burn-in period, where significant performance reduction occurs, was detected for all perovskite samples under test during the first days of exposure. However, for each perovskite sample this period differs. One important observation is the performance enhancement of the Silicon bottom cell in the tandem configuration (labeled as ETL3-Si) during the first days of exposure.

Fig. 1. Daily average power conversion efficiency (PCE) from perovskite mini-modules of different structure.

B. Diurnal Performance Degradation and Diurnal Performance Recovery

The diurnal efficiency degradation of all modules under test was calculated for each day in the field to investigate any possible trend between the perovskites with different ETL

layers. The diurnal efficiency degradation was calculated based on the efficiency values at the beginning and the end of each day at the same irradiance level. The overnight recovery was calculated using the efficiency values at the beginning of the next day and the final values of the previous day. The values of both diurnal degradation and diurnal recovery have been normalized to the initial efficiency value to have comparable results. The results for diurnal performance degradation and recovery for the perovskite top junctions in the tandem configuration can be found in Fig.2. This figure demonstrates that in most instances the normalized diurnal degradation values lie in the range between 0-0.3 indicating that the perovskite loses up to 30% of their initial performance over the day. The mini-module ETL3_C presents negative diurnal degradation and recovery over the day giving evidence of performance enhancement over the day and a corresponding performance reduction over the night which is not presented in other modules of the same series. A detailed statistical analysis of the diurnal degradation and recovery values for the different modules was conducted and their correlation with temperature and irradiance will be described in the full manuscript.

Fig. 2. (a) Diurnal performance degradation and (b) Diurnal Performance Recovery overnight for the first 6-months of testing of the perovskite top junctions in tandem configuration samples.

Apart from the performance, the diurnal changes in current, voltage and Fill Factor (FF) have been calculated for the different structures for each day in the field using statistical analysis. Results have shown that current is the main parameter that drives the diurnal performance degradation over the day. Investigation of diurnal changes in hysteresis index suggests this is larger in the morning hours where performance is higher. Our dataset has shown various diurnal performance patterns over time for each sample that can be categorized into different groups. An unsupervised machine learning method called TSClust was utilized to obtain diurnal performance curve shape clusters from the outdoor dataset,

where we were able to identify the dominant shapes of diurnal performance curves.

C. Impact of temperature

The impact of temperature on the major electrical parameters of the devices was thoroughly investigated outdoors. The temperature coefficients of maximum power (P_{\max}) and open circuit-voltage (V_{oc}) were extracted from the outdoor data using linear regression analysis. Power temperature coefficient of ETL1_A sample demonstrated positive values over the timespan of outdoor testing due to light soaking and metastability effects occurring during the day while the power temperature coefficient for ETL2_A, which presented lower diurnal changes over the day and hence lower metastability effects, presented positive values in winter and negative values in the summer (see Fig.3). The calculation of power temperature coefficients for the tandem configuration is still in progress and will reveal the temperature behavior of perovskite top junction in those structures. Open-circuit voltage temperature coefficient values were calculated for the ETL2_A sample. Voltage temperature coefficient value for ETL2_A perovskite sample extracted outdoor over several months of testing was found to agree with the value obtained from indoor laboratory testing.

Fig. 3. Maximum Power (P_{\max}) temperature coefficient (in $W/^{\circ}C$) at different months of testing for sample ETL2_A over a year alongside with the temperature levels of the testing location.

C. Perovskite Performance Forecasting

The perovskite power output time series forecast was constructed for the ETL1 perovskite sample which presented the longest outdoor lifetime. Different methods (statistical and machine learning) were used to forecast the power output of the perovskite device. In particular, the seasonal autoregressive integrating moving average (SARIMA) model and the Facebook prophet (FBP) statistical methods have been utilized. The FBP statistical method (see Fig.4) identified a

downward output power trend forecasting that an output power value of roughly 0.013W would be reached by the end of 2024. Furthermore, machine learning methods using the eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) regression model has been utilized for predicting the output power time-series of perovskite sample. The proposed model achieved a normalized Root Mean Square Error (nRMSE) lower than 3% when applied to the test set dataset giving evidence of good agreement between the actual and predicted power.

Fig. 4. Perovskite power output time series forecast for sample ETL1_A using Facebook Prophet statistical method.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Several perovskite samples were tested outdoors for a duration of one to two years. Diurnal performance and recovery changes were calculated for the different samples and demonstrated diurnal values for degradation and recovery up to 30%. Temperature effects on the output power were studied and indicated the interplay of metastability and temperature effects depending on the ambient temperature level. Perovskite power output time series forecast was implemented using statistical (FBP) and machine learning methods (XGBoost regression model). Very low nRMSE value found between the actual and predicted power output giving evidence of good agreement between the actual and predicted power.

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